

Cherenkov-Channeling radiation from sub-GeV relativistic electrons

K.B. Korotchenko^{a,*}, Yu.L. Pivovarov^a, Y. Takabayashi^b, S.B. Dabagov^{c,d,e}^a National Research Tomsk Polytechnic University, 30 Lenin Ave., 634050 Tomsk, Russia^b SAGA Light Source, 8-7 Yayoigaoka, Tosu, Saga 841-0005, Japan^c INFN - Laboratori Nazionali di Frascati, Via E. Fermi 40, I-00044, Frascati (RM), Italy^d RAS - P.N. Lebedev Physical Institute, Leninsky Pr. 53, 119991 Moscow, Russia^e NR Nuclear University MEPhI, Kashirskoe Sh. 31, 115409 Moscow, Russia

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 22 March 2019

Received in revised form 13 May 2019

Accepted 17 June 2019

Available online 8 July 2019

Editor: L. Rolandi

Keywords:

Cherenkov radiation

Channeling radiation

Mixed Cherenkov-Channeling radiation

ABSTRACT

Quantization of transverse energy levels for planar channeled relativistic electrons together with crystal dispersion may drastically change Cherenkov radiation resulting in mixed Cherenkov-Channeling Radiation (ChCR). In this work we have developed a quantum theory of ChCR. We have shown that the main feature of ChCR is reflected by its angular distribution, which consists of narrow bands reflecting the quantization of the projectile transverse energy. Moreover, mixed ChCR is shifted compared to Cherenkov radiation to larger emission angles. To stimulate experimental investigation of predicted phenomenon, a numerical analysis is carried out for 255 MeV electrons planar channeled in C (diamond) and Si crystals.

© 2019 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). Funded by SCOAP³.

1. Introduction

Over the last years the series of successful experiments on interaction of relativistic electrons with aligned crystals have been performed at the SAGA-LS facility. The results of these experiments are reflected in publications on the observation of quantum effects for parametric X-ray radiation at channeling (PXRC) [1–3], on the study of Cherenkov radiation (ChR) in a diamond crystal [4], on the investigations of sub-GeV electrons scattering [5] and rainbow scattering [6] by thin and ultrathin crystals.

Despite the number of theoretical and experimental works on channeling radiation (CR), see e.g. [7–14], some features of CR are not studied up to date. Indeed, to outline both spectral and angular distributions of large-angle (close to Cherenkov one) optical and ultraviolet CR by relativistic channeled electrons in optically transparent crystals is still opened task. In the meantime, the optical radiation from channeled particles was first discussed in [15] revealing the general formulas, while in [16] the modified CR theory, taking into account the experimentally obtained crystal dispersion, was presented. The latter becomes important for getting theoretical basics to planned experiments.

As known, relativistic electron moving in a medium by rectilinear trajectory emits ChR in optical and ultraviolet regions, various behaviors of which have been discussed in many publications (see,

for instance, in [17–27]). In aligned crystals the electron trajectory may become undulating with high frequency and small amplitude that is realized at channeling conditions. Thus, the projectile motion in a channeling regime changes the rectilinear trajectory to quasi-periodic one. Due to the channeling undulation, the projectile (electron, in our case) emits the CR-photons. Typically, CR is associated with the emission in forward direction (respect to the projectile longitudinal momentum along the crystal channeling direction). However, CR can be also observed at large angles close to Cherenkov angle. Since these two types of radiations cannot be separated in that case, in principle, at large angles the radiation by channeled particle is composed by proper CR in combination with ChR at channeling (the possibility for ChR at channeling has been first mentioned in [28]), i.e., we deal with a new type of radiation, mixed Cherenkov-Channeling Radiation (ChCR).

For example, let remind that similar mixed radiation, i.e. Synchrotron-Cherenkov Effect, has been studied both theoretically and experimentally in detail (see, in [29–32]). Two types of mixed radiation by relativistic heavy ions (RHI), i.e. transition-bremsstrahlung and Cherenkov-bremsstrahlung have been considered in [33] and in [34–40], respectively. The first theoretical model of ChCR by RHI based on classical electrodynamics is discussed in [41] paying attention to necessary corrections to be done for ordinary ChR.

And finally, in [16] the quantum theory of ChCR by sub-GeV electrons has been developed. In that work within the frame of quantum electrodynamics new formulae describing the large-angle

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: korotchenko@tpu.ru (K.B. Korotchenko).

photon emission by channeled electrons was first obtained taking into account the refractive index dispersion. However, all calculations for both the matrix element and the form-factor were performed within first order approximation, so-called dipole approximation. Thus, it was not explicitly shown that newly described radiation is a mixed radiation, i.e. a term ChCR was not introduced.

In this work we demonstrate the applicability of general expressions derived for describing both CR and ChR in two limiting cases. The features of angular and spectral distributions of ChCR are underlined and successfully illustrated via numerical calculations of ChCR in ultrathin diamond and Si crystals, making up in such a way future experimental studies.

2. Basics of the ChCR quantum theory

In the first order perturbation theory the matrix element for the probability of ChCR can be presented by the following general expression

$$dw_{if} = \frac{e^2}{2\pi\hbar} P_i(\theta_0) \sum_{\tau} |\mathbf{e}_{\tau} \alpha_{if}|^2 \delta(\kappa_{if} - \kappa) \frac{d^3\kappa}{\kappa}, \quad (1)$$

where e and \hbar are the electron charge and Planck constant, correspondingly, $\tau = (\sigma, \pi)$ is an index denoting the components of polarization vector \mathbf{e}_{τ} for CR photon, $\kappa = |\kappa| = \omega/c^*$, $c^* \hbar \kappa_{if} = (E_i - E_f)$ with the phase velocity of CR photon in a crystal $c^* = c/n(\omega)$, and $E_{i(f)} \simeq \varepsilon_{i(f)} + c(p_{i(f)z}^2 + m^2 c^2)^{1/2}$ is the total relativistic energy of channeled electron in initial i and final f quantum transverse states with corresponding transverse energies $\varepsilon_{i(f)}$. The vector components α_{if} for the case of planar channeling are defined as follows [16]:

$$\begin{aligned} (\alpha_{if})_x &= -\mathbf{i}\langle x \rangle_{if} \frac{\Omega_{if}}{c}, \quad \langle x \rangle_{if} = \langle f | x e^{-i\kappa_x x} | i \rangle, \\ (\alpha_{if})_y &= 0, \\ (\alpha_{if})_z &= -\mathbf{i}\langle F \rangle_{if} \beta, \quad \langle F \rangle_{if} = \mathbf{i}\langle f | e^{-i\kappa_x x} | i \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

with $\hbar\Omega_{if} = \varepsilon_i - \varepsilon_f$, $\langle F \rangle_{if}$ is the transition form-factor, which at $i = f$ is simply the form-factor of i -th quantum state for planar channeled electron, $\langle x \rangle_{if}$ is the transition matrix element, $\kappa_x = |\kappa| \sin\theta \cos\varphi$.

Although both the transition form-factor $\langle F \rangle_{if}$ and the matrix element $\langle x \rangle_{if}$ are not explicitly influenced by the frequency Ω_{if} , the presence of δ -function in Eq. (1) makes them frequency dependent. Thus, integrating Eq. (1) over all azimuthal φ and polar $\theta \in (\theta, \theta + \Delta\theta)$ angles we can derive the expression for the number of photons emitted by channeled electron per unit path at its transition $i \rightarrow f$ between the quantum states of transverse motion

$$\begin{aligned} dN_{if}^{\omega} &= \frac{1}{c\hbar} \frac{dw_{if}}{d\omega\Delta\theta} = \\ &= \frac{\alpha}{c\hbar} \frac{\Omega_{if}^2}{2c^2 n^2 \beta^3 \omega} P_i(\theta_0) G(\omega) \Theta(W_{\Delta}) \Theta(W_0) \times \\ &\times \left[(2c^2 \beta F_{if}^2 - x_{if}^2 \Omega_{if}^2) \times \right. \\ &\left. \left[\left(1 - \frac{2\omega}{\Omega_{if}^m} + \left(\frac{\omega}{\Omega_{if}^m} \right)^2 \right) - 2n^2 \beta^2 \frac{\omega}{\Omega_{if}^2} \left(1 - \frac{\omega}{2\Omega_{if}^m} \right) \right] - \right. \\ &\left. - 2n^2 \beta^2 \omega^2 x_{if}^2 \right], \\ G(\omega) &= 1 + \frac{\omega}{n(\omega)} \frac{\partial n}{\partial \omega}, \quad \Omega_{if}^m = \frac{\Omega_{if}}{1 - n^2(\omega)\beta^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Here, $P_i(\theta_0)$ stands for the initial population of i -th transverse quantum state as a function of the angle of incidence $\theta_0 =$

$\arctan[p_x/p_z]$ with respect to the channeling planes, α is the fine-structure constant. The arguments of the Heaviside's functions $\Theta(\dots)$ are defined by the dependences

$$\begin{aligned} W_{\Delta} &= \frac{\Omega_{if}}{1 - n(\omega)\beta \cos(\theta + \Delta\theta)} - \omega, \\ W_0 &= \omega - \frac{\Omega_{if}}{1 - n(\omega)\beta \cos\theta} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Since we deal with the radiation emission, i.e. $W_0 \geq 0$, the emission angle should fulfill the condition

$$\cos\theta \leq \frac{1}{n(\omega)\beta} \left(1 - \frac{\Omega_{if}}{\omega} \right), \quad (5)$$

which differs from the standard Cherenkov angle $\cos\theta_{Ch} = 1/n(\omega)\beta$ (the resonance case) in the deviation parameter Ω_{if}/ω .

Eq. (3) is presented in the form that permits performing simple transition from ChCR to CR. Indeed, if we take both functions $\langle F \rangle_{if}$ and $\langle x \rangle_{if}$ in dipole approximation, after some algebra it reduces to the expression for CR-photon number first reported in [8]. However, the presence in Eq. (3) of the form-factor $\langle F \rangle_{if}$ allows rewriting this equation in a different, but analytically equivalent, form

$$\begin{aligned} dN_{if}^{\omega} &= \frac{\alpha}{c\hbar} \beta P_i(\theta_0) G(\omega) \times \\ &\times \left[\left(1 - \frac{1}{n^2 \beta^2} \right) F_{if}^2 + \frac{F_{if}^2}{n^2 \beta^2} \left(\frac{2\Omega_{if}}{\omega} - \frac{\Omega_{if}^2}{\omega^2} \right) + \right. \\ &\left. + \frac{x_{if}^2 \Omega_{if}^2}{2\beta^2 c^2} \left(n^2 \beta^2 + 1 - \frac{2\Omega_{if}}{\omega} + \frac{\Omega_{if}^2}{\omega^2} \right) \frac{1}{n^2 \beta^2} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where for the convenience of perception the Heaviside's functions $\Theta(\dots)$ are not shown. To transform further this general expression to that, which corresponds to the standard ChR formula, we have to consider the intraband transitions $i \rightarrow i$ with $\Omega_{ii} \rightarrow 0$ (i.e. $\kappa_x \rightarrow 0$), and $F_{ii}^2 \simeq 1$ as reduced from (2). As a result, Eq. (6) can be simplified to

$$dN_{ii}^{\omega} \simeq \frac{\alpha_0}{c\hbar} \beta P_i(\theta_0) \left(1 - \frac{1}{n^2 \beta^2} \right) G(\omega), \quad (7)$$

which at the condition (5) takes the form

$$dN_{ii}^{\omega} \simeq \frac{\alpha}{c\hbar} \beta P_i(\theta_0) \sin^2 \theta_{Ch} G(\omega), \quad (8)$$

where θ_{Ch} is the Cherenkov angle.

After summing up over populated channeling quantum states $\sum_i P_i(\theta_0) = 1$ one obtains the formula, which exactly (at $G(\omega) = 1$) coincides with the one for ChR angular distribution within standard theory (see, for instance, in [17–19,42,43]).

Hence, the results obtained prompt the conclusion on a new type of radiation, i.e. mixed Cherenkov-Channeling Radiation (ChCR).

3. Index of refraction for Si and C (diamond)

The experimentally measured dependences of refractive index $n = n(\omega)$ of Si and diamond (C) crystals for optical and near ultraviolet frequencies (Si - red line, diamond (C) - blue dashed line) in the photon energy in range $\hbar\omega \in (1, 12)$ eV are shown in Fig. 1a [44].

In Fig. 1a one may see that the variation range $n(\omega)$ for Si, $n(\omega) = 1 \div 6.7$ is much greater than that for C, $0.46 \div 3.5$. Additionally, we have to point out, the value for index of refraction remains constant only for C in the range $\hbar\omega \in (0.2, 3)$ eV,

Fig. 1. a) Index of refraction $n = n(\omega)$ for Si (solid line) and C (diamond - dashed line) [44]. The regions of anomalous dispersion ($\partial n/\partial\omega < 0$) are underlined; b) The refractive index derivative $\partial n/\partial\omega$ for Si (solid line) and C (diamond - dashed line): the positions for $\partial n/\partial\omega = 0$ are indicated by vertical lines.

Fig. 2. Dependences of polar angles θ on ChCR-photon energies $\hbar\omega$ calculated for Si (a) and diamond (b) crystals (electron energy 255 MeV). Dashed line presents the ChCR-photon angles calculated according Eq. (5) with $\Omega_{ii} = 0$ and $n(\omega)$ taken from Fig. 1.

while becomes rapidly increasing for $\hbar\omega \in (1.3, 3.3)$ eV in Si and $\hbar\omega \in (3.3, 7.2)$ eV in C, as well as - rapidly decreasing for $\hbar\omega \in (3.3, 6)$ eV in Si and $\hbar\omega \in (11.2, 13)$ eV in C.

We have also to underline the presence for both crystals the regions of anomalous dispersion $\partial n/\partial\omega < 0$ [15,20,45–50], which are separately emphasized in Fig. 1. To analyze ChCR spectral and angular properties (see in Eqs. (3), (6)) aforementioned features of the refraction indexes for both crystals should be correctly taken into account.

4. Kinematics for ChCR

The conditions for ChCR have been defined in Sec. 2, main features for which come from simple formulas (4). However, in order to get the band structure due to the projectile channeling, it becomes necessary carrying out rather routine calculations to solve the quantum equation of motions [16,51,52]. The latter provides us with the wave functions and energies of the quantum levels for channeled projectiles and then with the transition energies Ω_{if} .

We have analyzed the case of 255 MeV channeled electrons (the linac of SAGA-LS accelerator facility). In our calculations we have presented every band as a set of 11 subbands. Hence, since the number of energy bands equals 15 for (110) Si and 11 for (110) C, the total number of quantum states is defined by 15×11 for (110) Si and 11×11 for (110) C. The results of calculations performed for a photon beam collimator of $\Delta\theta = 0.3$ mrad are shown in Fig. 2 as contour maps.

The lowermost lines of finite width in Fig. 2 correspond exceptionally to $i \rightarrow i$ transitions (intraband transitions).

The vertical black line (left) drawn at $\hbar\omega = 2.07$ eV (wavelength $\lambda \simeq 600$ nm) intersects allowed emission angles regions and well pronounced gaps: from $\theta \simeq 75^\circ$ in the case of Si and $\theta \simeq 65^\circ$ in the case of C. Then one may suggest, the ChCR angular distribution should consist of well pronounced several broad peaks (the first of them is located just near the corresponding to $\lambda \simeq 600$ nm Cherenkov angle for Si) and almost continuous (gapless) spectrum at greater angles. This simple prediction is confirmed by exact calculation for Si (Fig. 3).

5. ChCR by sub-GeV electrons in a thin Si crystal

The use of Eq. (3) or Eq. (6) requires very time-consuming computer calculations. First we have to determine the wave functions and band structure for the transverse energy levels of channeled electrons. Then it will be followed by calculation of the transition form-factor F_{if} and matrix elements x_{if} as defined by Eq. (2). Due to the small energy of ChCR-photon with respect to the energy of relativistic channeled electron, the matrix elements x_{if} and F_{if} are calculated in dipole approximation. Thus, the number of ChCR-photons emitted at the polar angles $\theta \neq \theta_{Ch}$ is obtained in dipole approximation ($i \neq f$), while the number of ChCR-photons when the initial state coincides with the final one ($i = f$) - using Eq. (7).

Considering all these factors we can get a final formula to calculate the intensity of ChCR spectral distribution within a solid angle $\Delta\omega$ that is similar to Eq. (14) in [16]

$$\frac{dI_{if}}{d\omega\Delta\omega} = \frac{e^2 x_{if}^2 \Omega_{if}^2}{4c^3 \pi \beta^3 n^2(\omega)} P_i(\theta_0) G(\omega) \omega \Theta(W_\Delta) \Theta(W_0) \times \left[\Delta^+ \left(1 - 2 \frac{\omega}{\Omega_{if}^m} + \left(\frac{\omega}{\Omega_{if}^m} \right)^2 \right) + n^2(\omega) \beta^2 \Delta^- \right] \quad (9)$$

Summing up over all transitions between quantum states of a channeled electron, we successfully can define the photon number emitted by electron per unit path within a cone $\Delta\omega$

$$dN = \sum_{i,f} \frac{1}{c\hbar} \frac{1}{\hbar\omega} \frac{dI_{if}}{d\omega\Delta\omega} \quad (10)$$

As seen, the number of ChCR-photons is a function of two parameters, the polar emission angle θ and the energy of ChCR photons $dN = f(\theta, \hbar\omega)$. The Figs. 3–5 make evident these specific dependences.

Moreover, the positions for large peaks in Figs. 3 and 4, are within the area of allowed emission angles that is in accordance with the graphs in Fig. 2. Similar distribution for photon energy $\hbar\omega \simeq 2.07$ eV (wavelength $\lambda \simeq 600$ nm) is shown in Fig. 4, from

Fig. 3. ChCR angular distributions for (220) channeled 255 MeV electrons a) for the ChCR-photon energy $\hbar\omega \simeq 3.3$ eV (wavelength $\lambda \simeq 375.7$ nm) in Si; b) for the ChCR-photon energy $\hbar\omega \simeq 7.2$ eV (wavelength $\lambda \simeq 172.2$ nm) in diamond (C).

Fig. 4. ChCR angular distributions for Si (220) channeled 255 MeV electrons for the ChCR-photon energy $\hbar\omega \simeq 2.07$ eV (wavelength $\lambda \simeq 600$ nm). The position of Cherenkov angle $\theta_{ch} \simeq 75.3^\circ$ is indicated by arrow.

which we can resolve two main peaks angularly separated in accordance with Fig. 2a.

The spectral distributions of ChCR-photons emitted by 255 MeV (220) electrons planar channeled in Si crystal at fixed polar angles $\theta \simeq 78.7^\circ$ and $\theta \simeq 80.3^\circ$ (corresponding to the case of Fig. 4) are formed by single peaks of finite width, respectively, revealing wherein specific behaviors of ChCR (Fig. 5).

Using Eq. (7) one can calculate the number of ChCR-photons emitted at intraband transitions ($i \rightarrow i$). The number of these photons (i.e. ChR-photons) with the energy $\hbar\omega \simeq 2.07$ eV emitted at the angle $\theta \simeq 75.3^\circ$ is $dN \simeq 0.16$ ph/(eV cm) that more than 40 times less of ChCR-photons at the same conditions.

6. Discussion on characteristic lengths

In sections 4-5 we have evaluated some ChCR features for fixed electron beam energy and chosen crystal thickness. These results confirm the need to study the new type of radiation analyzing in detail its dependence on main parameters, such as the beam energy, the crystal thickness and the radiation emission wavelength. It becomes also important to understand the relationship between these parameters in definition of ChCR.

Let apply the concept of specific characteristic lengths for our analysis. Wherein we can establish two types of the length, one is related to the behaviors of electron scattering, other - to those of ChCR formation and attenuation.

6.1. Thin and ultrathin crystals at channeling

Let start with the length characterizing the electrons channeling. In the literature one can find several definitions such as a thin crystal when the projectile dechanneling is neglected, a thick crystal when the dechanneling should be taken into account, a ultrathin crystal, indeed a very thin crystal, when a particle makes a part of its complete oscillation in a planar channel during its

motion down to the crystal exit. For instance, a Half-Wave Crystal (HWC), at which the projectile trajectory in a crystal is a half of the channeling length, is a very recent trend in high-energy channeling as it allows the beams deflection/splitting (see, e.g. in Refs. [53–56]) practically without essential scattering. We do not deal with HWC in our discussion below.

Assuming the channeling regime is established, we consider the electron with many oscillations done in a planar channel during its motion in a crystal. At classical description the electron oscillation period can be estimated as $T \simeq d/\beta c\theta_c$, $L_z = \beta cT = \pi d/\theta_c$, therefore $N \simeq L/L_z = (L/d)\theta_c \gg 1$. Here we have used the definitions for the characteristic channeling length L_z , which corresponds to the channeling period T , and the number of oscillations N . Thus, at the well established channeling regime the crystal thickness should be $L \gg d/\theta_c$, where θ_c is the planar channeling critical angle

$$\theta_c = \sqrt{\frac{2U_0}{E}} = \sqrt{\frac{2U_0}{\gamma mc^2}} \quad (11)$$

with the electron energy E , relativistic factor γ , electron rest mass m and the depth of planar channeling potential U_0 , which equals to $U_0 \simeq 21.2$ eV for Si (110) and $U_0 \simeq 23.6$ eV for C (110).

On the other hand, for effective channeling the thickness L of the crystal should not exceed the dechanneling length l_d defined as a length, at which scattering at channeling θ_c and multiple scattering [42]

$$\theta_{MS}(l) = \frac{13.6 \text{ MeV}}{\beta cp} Z \sqrt{\frac{l}{X_0}} \left[1 + 0.038 \log \frac{l}{X_0} \right] \quad (12)$$

result in equal scattering angle

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_c = \theta_c(l_d) \rightarrow \\ \frac{Z^2 l_d}{X_0} = \left(\frac{\beta cp}{13.6 \text{ MeV}} \right)^2 \frac{2U_0}{\gamma mc^2} = \frac{2U_0 \beta^4 \gamma mc^2}{(13.6 \text{ MeV})^2}, \\ l_d = \frac{X_0 2U_0 \beta^4 \gamma mc^2}{Z^2 (13.6 \text{ MeV})^2} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

The radiation lengths X_0 for the crystals under consideration are $\simeq 9.4$ cm (Si) and $\simeq 12.13$ cm (C) that for the case $\gamma mc^2 = 255$ MeV, $\beta \simeq 1$, $Z = 1$ gives us the following dechanneling lengths, $l_d \simeq 5.5$ μm (Si) and $l_d \simeq 7.9$ μm (C).¹

Therefore, we can conclude that to observe ChCR the crystal length should be limited by two specific lengths, the 1st one to provide stable particle channeling ($L \gg d/\theta_c$), while the 2nd one avoids its dechanneling ($L < l_d$). For our case:

¹ It means the thin Si crystal ($L = 0.76$ μm) already used in a Rainbow Scattering experiment [56] is quite suitable for observation of the ChCR features predicted.

Fig. 5. ChCR-photons spectral distribution for Si (220) channeled 255 MeV electrons at polar angles $\theta \simeq 78.7^\circ$ (a) and $\theta \simeq 80.3^\circ$ (b). The points corresponding to the ChCR-photons energy $\hbar\omega \simeq 2.07$ eV are indicated by vertical lines.

Fig. 6. The function d/θ_c and the dechanneling length l_d vs the electron energy $E = \gamma mc^2$.

- $5.5 \mu\text{m} > L \gg 0.3 \mu\text{m}$ (C);
- $7.9 \mu\text{m} > L \gg 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ (Si).

For clarity, Fig. 6 shows the dependence d/θ_c as well as the dechanneling length l_d on the electron energy $E = \gamma mc^2$.

6.2. The length of radiation emission

The concept of formation length for radiation was first introduced by Frank (see in Ref. [57,58]) to interpret the origin of Cherenkov radiation. Originally, it was called a *Fresnel zone* and defined as the path of a charged particle moving with a constant velocity, for which the phase difference for the waves emitted at the ends of trajectory is less than

$$l = \frac{\pi \beta c}{\omega [1 - \beta n(\omega) \cos \theta]} \quad (14)$$

From general considerations we cannot define a moment (point) of emission, hence, as pointed by Frank, $l \rightarrow \infty$, which is valid at the ChR condition $1 - \beta n(\omega) \cos \theta = 0$.

Later on in [59,60] this idea was extended for small-angle radiation by high-energy particles moving along arbitrary trajectory in the following

$$l_{ph} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \mathbf{v} \exp[\mathbf{i}(\omega t - \mathbf{k}\mathbf{r}(t))] dt, \quad (15)$$

$$k = \omega n(\omega)/c$$

In many cases this integral reduces to the contribution of a small number of the Fresnel zones, and the expressions (14) and (15) become of the same order of magnitude. The concept of formation length makes quick qualitative and quantitative conclusions on the features of radiation for given trajectory $\mathbf{r}(t)$ and velocity $\mathbf{v}(t)$ easily done.

The radiation intensity defined by

$$\frac{dW(\omega, \mathbf{k})}{d\omega d\Omega} = \frac{Z^2 e^2}{4\pi^2 c^2} |\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{l}_{ph}|^2 \quad (16)$$

are higher at larger l_{ph} . It is important to underline that for high-energy particles and small-angle scattering l_{ph} can reach macroscopic values [59,60].

In our case of large-angle emission and $|\mathbf{v}(t)| \simeq v_z$ one can obtain the well-known formula for angular distribution of ChR

$$\frac{dW(\omega, \mathbf{k})}{d\omega d\Omega} = \frac{Z^2 e^2}{4\pi^2 c^2} \left(l \frac{n\omega}{c} \sin \theta \right)^2, \quad (17)$$

$$l = \int_0^T \exp[\mathbf{i}(\omega t - n(\omega) \cos \theta)] dt$$

For the quantum theory of ChCR the valuable for calculations matrix elements (see Eq. (2)) are reduced in the quasi-classical limit to the equations containing similar to (15) lengths with obvious replacement, reflecting the influence of channeling (see Eq. (4))

$$\omega \rightarrow \omega - \Omega_{if} \quad (18)$$

Then, the formation length l_{ph} (photon energies are of order of several eV) becomes large for both emissions at Cherenkov angle and at the angles greater than Cherenkov one. Finally, for these emission angles l_{ph} practically does not depend on relativistic factor γ , while d/θ_c and l_d reveal rapid increase with γ . Comparing these lengths allows us to conclude that the condition $d/\theta_c \ll L < l_d$ for sub-GeV electrons is stronger than $L < l_{ph}$.

6.3. Thin and ultrathin crystals for optical properties

Once ChCR is emitted in a crystal, it would be detectable only if not absorbed by the crystal. At theoretical analysis this fact can be included into consideration via crystal transmittance function $T(\omega, l)$, which depends on the photon energy and the length of the photon path in a crystal. In a simplest way in order to perform all calculations taking into account the radiation absorption, Eqs. (3) and (6) could be multiplied by the empirically drawn transmittance function $T(\omega, l)$. ChCR waves are continuously emitted by electron along all its trajectory inside the crystal-radiator. Obviously, corresponding photons cover different distances $L_{ph} = L/\cos \theta$ inside the radiator. Hence, for the crystal thickness $L = 0.74 \mu\text{m}$ ChCR photons travel inside the crystal within the distance range $L_{ph} \in (0.8, 1.2) \mu\text{m}$.

The transmittance functions $T(\omega)$ based on experimental data [44] are plotted in Fig. 7 at various crystal thicknesses for Si and diamond crystals. The dependences are shown for the energy range $\hbar\omega \in (2, 7)$ eV used for our analysis in previous sections.

Fig. 7. Transmittance $T = T(\omega)$ for Si (a) and diamond (b) crystals for five various thicknesses (compilation of experimental data [44]).

As seen, a Si crystal of $L < 5 \mu\text{m}$ thickness is transparent for photons $\hbar\omega < 2.5 \text{ eV}$ ($\lambda > 200 \text{ nm}$) (Fig. 6a), while a diamond (C) crystal independently on its thickness becomes transparent for higher energies $\hbar\omega < 5.6 \text{ eV}$ (Fig. 6b). Moreover, the 50% transmittance and more, $T(\omega) > 0.5$, can be detected for photons $\hbar\omega \simeq 5.6 \div 6.8 \text{ eV}$ in crystals of $L = 5 \div 0.5 \mu\text{m}$.

This analysis proves the fact that both C and Si crystals can be used for ChCR detection. However, it should be underlined that ChCR-photons per unit path is greater in Si (Fig. 3) because of greater values of the refractive index $n(\omega)$ for Si crystal with respect to C one (Fig. 1).

For example, following recent experimental studies, let choose ChCR-photons with energy $\hbar\omega = 2.07 \text{ eV}$ ($\lambda = 600 \text{ nm}$) emitted in ultrathin crystal $L = 0.74 \mu\text{m}$ [4,38]. At the radiation emission angle $\theta = 75.4^\circ$ the number of photons per unit length will be $dN \simeq 13 \text{ ph/eV}$ and $dN_T \simeq 8.34 \text{ ph/eV}$ with the crystal transmittance $T(\omega)$ taken into account.

The discussion on various characteristic lengths is important to stress their influence on possible experimental arrangements to study ChCR features.

7. Resume

The large-angle radiation emission by relativistic channeled electrons in optically transparent thin crystals may result in a new type of radiation, mixed Cherenkov-Channeled Radiation (ChCR). New phenomenon can be explained within both classical and quantum approximations. However, specific features of ChCR are due to the quantization of transverse energy levels of planar channeled relativistic electrons as well as the crystal dispersion. We have shown that ChCR angular distribution consists of the series of peaks shifted to larger emission angles with respect to known ChR. General expressions derived from developed theory for ChCR have revealed in their limiting approximations the transition between “pure” CR and ChR. The numerical analyses done for the case of 255 MeV electron beam planar channeled in Si and C (diamond) crystals proves the feasibility of experimental studies for the features of ChCR.

Acknowledgements

The research is carried out at Tomsk Polytechnic University within the framework of Tomsk Polytechnic University Competitiveness Enhancement Program grant. One of the authors (SBD) would like to acknowledge the support by the Competitiveness Program of National Research Nuclear University MEPhI (Moscow). Two of the authors (KBK and YLP) express their gratitude to Dr. T.A. Tukhfatullin for the useful discussions.

References

[1] K.B. Korotchenko, Y.L. Pivovarov, Y. Takabayashi, JETP Lett. 95 (2012) 433.

[2] K.B. Korotchenko, Y.L. Pivovarov, Y. Takabayashi, Nucl. Instrum. Methods B 309 (2013) 25.
 [3] Y. Takabayashi, K.B. Korotchenko, Y.L. Pivovarov, Nucl. Instrum. Methods B 315 (2013) 105.
 [4] Y. Takabayashi, E.I. Fiks, Y.L. Pivovarov, Phys. Lett. A 379 (2015) 1032.
 [5] Y. Takabayashi, Y.L. Pivovarov, T.A. Tukhfatullin, Phys. Lett. A 378 (2014) 1520.
 [6] Y. Takabayashi, Y.L. Pivovarov, T.A. Tukhfatullin, Phys. Lett. B 785 (2018) 347.
 [7] V.A. Bazylev, N.K. Zhevago, Sov. Phys. JETP 46 (5) (1977) 891.
 [8] V.V. Beloshitskii, M.A. Kumakhov, Sov. Phys. JETP 47 (4) (1978) 652.
 [9] J.C. Kimball, N. Cue, Phys. Rep. 125 (2) (1985) 69.
 [10] M.A. Kumakhov, R. Weddel, Radiation of Relativistic Light Particles During Interaction with Single Crystals, Spectrum, Heidelberg, 1991.
 [11] A.I. Akhiezer, N.F. Shul'ga, High-Energy Electrodynamics in Matter, Gordon and Breach, Amsterdam, 1996.
 [12] V.N. Baier, V.M. Katkov, V.M. Strakhovenko, Electromagnetic Processes at High Energies in Oriented Single Crystals, World Scientific, Singapore, 1998.
 [13] S.B. Dabagov, N.K. Zhevago, Riv. Nuovo Cimento 31 (9) (2008) 491.
 [14] A.V. Korol, A.V. Soloviev, W. Greiner, Channeling and Radiation in Periodically Bent Crystals, Springer Series on Atomic, Optical and Plasma Physics, vol. 69, Springer-Verlag, Berlin-Heidelberg, 2013.
 [15] V.G. Baryshevsky Channeling, Radiation and Reactions in Crystals under High Energy, Moscow University Press, 1982, p. 256 (in Russian) (There is an author-made translation of this book: <http://inp.bsu.by/library/channeling1982-2016.pdf>).
 [16] K.B. Korotchenko, Yu.L. Pivovarov, Phys. Lett. A 382 (2018) 444.
 [17] B.M. Bolotovskii, Phys. Usp. 52 (2009) 1099.
 [18] G.N. Afanasiev, Vavilov-Cherenkov and Synchrotron Radiation, Springer Science & Business Media, 2004, p. 491.
 [19] J.D. Jackson, Classical Electrodynamics, 3rd edition, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1998.
 [20] V.L. Ginzburg, Theoretical Physics and Astrophysics, Additional Chapters, Nauka, Moscow, 1975, p. 416 (in Russian).
 [21] I.M. Frank, Vavilov-Cherenkov Radiation, Nauka, Moscow, 1988 (in Russian).
 [22] A.S. Vodopianov, et al., Nucl. Instrum. Methods B 201 (2003) 266.
 [23] J. Ruzicka, et al., Vacuum 63 (2001) 591.
 [24] N. Akchurin, Phys. Proc. 00 (2011) 1.
 [25] V.A. Dolgikh, E.G. Vyatkin, Russ. Phys. J. (1988) 137.
 [26] V.S. Malyshevsky, G.V. Fomin, I.A. Ivanova, JETP Lett. 43 (1) (2017) 61.
 [27] K.G. Dedrick, Phys. Rev. 87 (1952) 891.
 [28] V.V. Beloshitsky, S.B. Dabagov, Sov. Phys. Tech. Phys. 33 (1988) 939.
 [29] T. Erber, et al., Ann. Phys. 102 (1976) 405.
 [30] K.D. Bonin, et al., Phys. Rev. Lett. 57 (1986) 2264.
 [31] T.M. Rynne, J. Appl. Phys. 52 (1981) 6471.
 [32] T.M. Rynne, G.B. Baumgartner, T. Erber, J. Appl. Phys. 49 (4) (1978) 2233.
 [33] E.I. Fiks, Yu.L. Pivovarov, Nucl. Instrum. Methods B 355 (2015) 184.
 [34] V.R. Altapova, O.V. Bogdanov, Yu.L. Pivovarov, Nucl. Instrum. Methods B 267 (2009) 896.
 [35] E.I. Fiks, O.V. Bogdanov, Yu.L. Pivovarov, J. Phys. Conf. Ser. 357 (2012) 012002.
 [36] O.V. Bogdanov, E.I. Fiks, Yu.L. Pivovarov, J. Exp. Theor. Phys. 115 (3) (2012) 392.
 [37] E.I. Fiks, Y.L. Pivovarov, Russ. Phys. J. 56 (4) (2013) 456.
 [38] E.I. Fiks, Yu.L. Pivovarov, O.V. Bogdanov, H. Geissel, C. Scheidenberger, Nucl. Instrum. Methods B 309 (2013) 146.
 [39] E.I. Fiks, Yu.L. Pivovarov, O.V. Bogdanov, H. Geissel, C. Scheidenberger, J. Ruzicka, Nucl. Instrum. Methods B 314 (2013) 51.
 [40] E.I. Rozhkova, Yu.L. Pivovarov, Phys. Lett. A 380 (2016) 2386.
 [41] O.V. Bogdanov, E.I. Fiks, Yu.L. Pivovarov, Nucl. Instrum. Methods B 355 (2015) 86.
 [42] J. Beringer, et al., Particle data group, Phys. Rev. D 86 (2012) 010001.
 [43] C. Patrignani, et al., Particle Data Group, Chin. Phys. C 40 (2016) 100001.
 [44] M.N. Polyanskiy, Refractive index database, Available at: <http://refractiveindex.info>.
 [45] V.G. Baryshevsky, I.D. Feranchuk, A.P. Ulyanenko, Parametric X-Ray Radiation in Crystals, Theory, Experiment and Applications, Springer, 2005.

- [46] M. Shevelev, A. Konkov, A. Aryshev, *Phys. Rev. A* 92 (2015) 053851.
- [47] V.M. Grichine, *Radiat. Phys. Chem.* 67 (2003) 93.
- [48] H. Ren, X. Deng, Y. Zheng, N. An, X. Chen, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 108 (2012) 223901.
- [49] R.W. Boyd, *Nonlinear Optics*, 2nd ed., Academic Press, San Diego, CA, 2003.
- [50] N. An, Y. Zheng, H. Ren, X. Zhao, X. Deng, X. Chen, *Photon. Res.* 3 (4) (2015) 106.
- [51] S.B. Dabagov, L.I. Ognev, *Sov. Phys. Tech. Phys.* 33 (1988) 1025.
- [52] S.B. Dabagov, V.V. Beloshitsky, M.A. Kumakhov, *Nucl. Instrum. Methods B* 74 (1993) 368.
- [53] V. Guidi, et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 108 (2012) 014801.
- [54] W. Scandale, et al., *Phys. Lett. B* 734 (2014) 1.
- [55] Y. Takabayashi, Yu.L. Pivovarov, T.A. Tukhfatullin, *Phys. Lett. B* 751 (2015) 453.
- [56] Y. Takabayashi, Yu.L. Pivovarov, T.A. Tukhfatullin, *Phys. Lett. B* 785 (2018) 347.
- [57] I.M. Frank, *Izv. Akad. Nauk SSSR, Ser. Fiz.* 6 (1942) 3.
- [58] I.M. Frank, *Sov. Phys. Usp.* 22 (12) (1979) 975.
- [59] M.L. Ter-Mikaelian, *High Energy Electromagnetic Processes in Condensed Media*, Interscience Tracts in Physics and Astronomy, vol. 28, Wiley, NY, 1972.
- [60] B.M. Bolotovskii, *The Formation Length and Its Role in the Radiation of Moving Charges*, Proc. of the Lebedev Physical Institute, vol. 140, Nauka, Moscow, 1982, pp. 95–139 (in Russian).